

ACTIVE AND PASSIVE LISTENING

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Abstract: Effective communication is heavily reliant on the skill of listening. This article delves into the two primary types of listening: active listening and passive listening. Listening plays a vital role in effective communication, enabling individuals to understand and respond appropriately to messages conveyed. Active listening and passive listening, both of them represent two distinct approaches to this fundamental skill. Active listening involves fully engaging with the speaker, focusing on their message, and employing various techniques to demonstrate attentiveness and understanding, to provide verbal and nonverbal cues such as nodding, maintaining eye contact, and using affirmative responses to signal their engagement. This type of listening promotes mutual understanding and fosters effective communication. While passive listening involves receiving information without active participation, it may be insufficient in contexts that require deep understanding and engagement. This might occur in situations like listening to music without engaging and responding actively or a lecture where no one does participate.

Keywords: Active listening, strategies for active listening in IELTS, passive listening, Passive listening characteristics, differences.

Active Listening:

Active listening is a way of listening and responding to another person that improves mutual understanding. It is an important first step to defuse the situation and seek solutions to problems. It is characterized by focused attention, engagement, and empathetic response. It involves actively participating in the communication process, demonstrating understanding, and providing feedback to the speaker. Robin Abrahams and Boris Groyberg from Harvard Business School describe active listening as having three aspects: cognitive, emotional, and behavioral. Here's how they define each aspect in their article, "How to Become a Better Listener":

- **Cognitive:** Paying attention to all the information, both explicit and implicit, that you are receiving from the other person, comprehending, and integrating that information
- **Emotional:** Staying calm and compassionate during the conversation, including managing any emotional reactions (annoyance, boredom) you might experience
- **Behavioral:** Conveying interest and comprehension verbally and nonverbally

Strategies for active listening in IELTS:

1. Focusing your attention

The first pillar of active listening is staying focused, a must-have skill for achieving a remarkable IELTS Listening score. Make sure to eliminate distractions like notifications on other devices and create a dedicated environment to fully engage with your listening practice.

This approach of concentration not only enhances your active learning experience but also provides the focus needed to improve your listening capabilities.

2. Note-taking

Note-taking is a game-changing active learning strategy, especially if you're targeting a stellar IELTS Listening band score. Whether you're enrolled in an IELTS class or simply leveraging IELTS preparation resources online, capturing unfamiliar terms, key points, or phrases during your listening practice can dramatically improve your retention and understanding. By jotting down these nuggets of information, you're arming yourself to tackle the specific questions you'll encounter in the IELTS Listening section, thereby improving your chances of achieving a desirable IELTS band score.

3. Interactive engagement

If you're keen on elevating your IELTS Listening score, this active listening strategy is crucial. Interactive engagement means participating actively, for example by questioning the audio or making predictions and drawing conclusions related to the listening material, instead of just passively hearing it. This not only enriches your IELTS preparation material but also fortifies your skills needed to excel in the IELTS Listening section. This technique is woven into quality IELTS preparation courses and is a must-try during your free online IELTS mock test sessions or any other practice test and exam you undertake.

4. Summarising and reviewing content

Summarising and reviewing the content after each listening session is a cornerstone in active listening strategies. Taking a moment to encapsulate what you've absorbed not only helps in how you can improve your IELTS Listening skills but also aids in fortifying retention and comprehension. This active learning approach is often embedded in IELTS preparation courses and is a vital step to complete. It essentially acts as a self-assessment, giving you insights into your progress as you aim for that coveted IELTS band score in listening.

Passive listening:

The meaning of passive listening is to listen without asking questions or interrupting the speaker. It may even mean that you don't really understand what's being said. There are situations where passive listening is important and helpful. For instance, if you're giving a presentation or making a speech, you're likely to prefer an audience that doesn't provide feedback midway. Similarly, if you're meeting your manager for a performance appraisal, you'll listen first before you respond. Some examples of passive listening are listening to presentations, the radio and even watching movies. In the workplace, you have to strike a balance between passive and active listening depending on the situation. You have to pay attention to passive listening in communication at work because your actions can impact your performance and others in your team.

Passive listening characteristics:

The truth is, we all know whether or not people are listening. Here are some of the telltale signs of passive listening habits.

1. Lack of eye contact

One of the most obvious signs of passive listening is a lack of eye contact. When someone is not actively engaged in a conversation, they may avoid making eye contact with the speaker. Instead, their gaze may wander or they may focus on something else entirely.

2. Minimal or delayed responses

Passive listeners often give minimal or delayed responses to what's being said. They may offer short, generic answers or simply nod their head without contributing anything meaningful because they aren't actively processing or understanding the information.

3. Distracted behavior

Passive listeners may display distracted behavior during a conversation. They may fidget, play with their phone or computer, or engage in other activities that divert their attention away from the speaker.

4. Lack of follow-up questions

Active listeners typically ask follow-up questions to clarify information or show interest in the topic. Passive listeners, on the other hand, often fail to ask any questions or show curiosity about what is being discussed.

5. Daydreaming or zoning out

Another key sign of passive listening is daydreaming or zoning out. People may start doodling or tapping their fingers on the table as though listening to music. This kind of body language sends a clear signal that they are not giving the conversation their undivided attention.

6. Interrupting or talking over others

Passive listeners may interrupt or talk over others during a conversation, demonstrating a lack of respect for the speaker and their message. This behavior indicates that people are more focused on their own thoughts or opinions than they are on paying attention to others.

7. Forgetting or misinterpreting information

Passive listeners often have trouble recalling or accurately interpreting information that was shared during a conversation. This is because they were not actively processing or retaining the information while it was being presented. Their lack of engagement leads to gaps in their understanding and memory of the conversation.

Differences:

The points stated below discuss the difference between active listening and passive listening:

1. Active listening is when the listener in the communication absorbs all that is being spoken by the speaker, as well as makes effort to verify the facts by asking questions. On the other hand, passive listening is when the listener is physically present during the presentation but mentally absent, wherein all that is spoken by the speaker is heard by the listener but not absorbed.
2. While active listening is an interactive process, passive listening is a mechanical process.
3. In active listening, the listener encourages the speaker to speak up further, by showing interest in the conversation. As against, a passive listener often discourages the speaker by not focusing on the listening process and showing boredom and disinterest on his face.
4. Active listening is supported by nodding, eye contact, asking questions, if necessary, etc. On the contrary, passive listening is denoted by ungainly posture or looking here and there, etc.
5. Non-verbal clues shown by an active listener are – change in facial expression, rolling of eyes, showing interest by questioning or smiling, etc. On the other hand, passive listener generally exhibits non-verbal clues such as yawning, looking here and there, showing boredom, being silent etc.

Conclusion:

In a nutshell, listening is an attentive process, which requires a person to consciously think to listen properly. The degree of attentiveness has a crucial role to play in the process of listening. The difference between active and passive listening lies in the listener's attention and involvement in the conversation. Relatively, active listening is more effective and interactive way to communicate than passive listening. Active listening can help you comprehend the speaker's message, show that you are paying attention and demonstrate respect. Besides, active listening can help you improve your communication abilities, build trust, and make better decisions.

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